

The Effect Of Email On Students' Writing Skills At The Eighth Graders Of *Mts. Mu'allimat Nw Kelayu* In The School Year 2017-2018.

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Abstract: Writing is one of language skill that must be mastered by the language learners. The teacher must be selective in relevant methods, media and technique, that is can engage the students to be more effective and creative in achieve the goal of learning. One of the media that is used in language teaching is email, because, it may motivate and reinforce any language skill the students. And as graphic communication to give the certain message accurately and short with use the language it easy to be understand. The statement of the problems of this research are; (1) Is there any effect of email on students' writing skills at the eighth graders of *MTs. Mu'allimat NW Kelayu* in the school year 2017-2018? (2) To what extent is the effect of email on students' writing skills at the eighth graders of *MTs. Mu'allimat NW Kelayu* in the school year 2017-2018?. This study belongs to a pre experimental research. The population was the eighth grade students of *MTs. Mu'allimat NW Kelayu* consisting of two classes. However the present researcher just took one class as sample there were 20 students as the experimental class. To get the data, the present researcher used research instrument namely written test. The result of data analyze, the present researcher found out the result r_{test} was 0.52 and r_{table} was 0.38 with $df = 5\%$ from the total of sample was twenty students. It means r_{test} was higher than r_{table} ($0.52 > 0.38$). So that, the present researcher concluded alternative hypothesis (H_a) was accepted, and null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected. It means that there was effect of email on students' writing skills at the eighth graders of *MTs. Mu'allimat NW Kelayu* in the school year 2017-2018

Key Words: Email, Writing Skill

A. Introduction

In learning English, there are four skills which are necessary to be mastered by the learners, those skills are listening, speaking, reading, and writing. The four skill above cannot be separated. They are supporting each other. One of the language skills needed to be learned besides the other language skills is writing. It is the last

taught after the other language skills such as listening, speaking, and reading. Writing is very complex and sometimes difficult to teach, requiring mastery not only grammatical and rhetorical device, but also conceptual and judgmental elements.¹

Writing is used to communicate as a means to convey the knowledge or information about a given subject. For example, in the newspaper, the readers often find the article, which is consisted of someone's opinion or the scientist's invention, advertisement, and so forth. Those all are purposed to share information to each other. Since English has become one of the main languages in international communication, it has a very important role in technological and scientific advances.

Based on the interview with English teacher of *MTs. Mu'allimat NW Kelayu* the present researcher found that most of students got difficulties in writing. It can be seen from the data and some problems that the students confront in writing. Furthermore, it is hard for the students to get ideas. They cannot write smoothly because they did not know what they are wanted to express to develop the topic and they get stuck in the middle of writing. Especially in writing skills, the students got difficulty in verb, grammar, punctuation, spelling, vocabulary and how to use past tense. As a result, the students have no motivation to write, and writing becomes a boring and hard activity for them.

Related to the statement above the present researcher concludes, in the classroom, we face dozens of technique applied to the students' under the expectation that they are able to or easy to understand the lesson. As a teacher, it is necessary to find new teaching media to overcome the problems and not to forget to motivate the students. Some teachers have used games, pictures, songs, real object, cartoon, movie, tape recorder, television, facebook and email as their teaching media to grow the student creativity in learning process.

In this study, Email is chosen as a media for teaching writing skills. Media through email is one of the most important things for teachers to teaching writing effectively. Email is a computer based method of sending messages from one computer user to another. These messages usually consist of individual pieces of text which they can send to another computer user even if the other user is not logged in (i.e. using the computer) at the time you send your message. The message can then

¹Heaton, J. B. *Writing English language test*, (Singapore: Longman Group Limited, 1989), p. 135

be read at a later time. This procedure is analogous to sending and receiving a letter. Originally, email messages were restricted to simple text, but now many systems can handle more complicated formats, such as graphics and word processed documents. Email also can make the students do not bore for studying writing and developing their knowledge and skills, because email is a way that students can express their ideas.

Based on the explanations above, the present researcher wants to investigate a study entitled "The Effect of Email on Students' Writing Skills at the eighth graders of *MTs. Mu'allimat NW Kelayu* in the school year 2017-2018".

B. Statement of Problem

The research problem can be formulated as follows:

1. Is there any effect of email on students' writing skill at the eighth graders of *MTs. Mu'allimat NW Kelayu* in the school year 2017-2018?
2. To what extent is the effect of email on students' writing skill at the eighth graders of *MTs. Mu'allimat NW Kelayu* in the school year 2017-2018?

C. Review of Literature and Hypothesis

1. Writing Skills

a. Concepts of Writing

To be tightly structured, writing should contain logical or associative connections and transitions which clearly express the relationship of the ideas described. To be grammatically and syntactically correct, writing should stick to the rules of English Standard, including proper punctuation and spelling. If writers choose to use unconventional syntax, they should be able to justify their choices. To be substantive, writing should convey the impression that the writer is informed about the subject. The researcher needs not to be an authority on the subject but should demonstrate awareness of its significance and its implications within a specified context.

Informed writing might include any or all of the followings: citations of authorities, experiential evidence, and discussion of debatable issues related to it, and relevant questions it raises. To be interesting, writing should engage its readers

through original insights and precise, unclenched language expressed in a "human" voice. It should demonstrate the writer's awareness of the specific audience for whom she or he is writing (the audience's degree of knowledge of the subject as well as its age, ethnic background, gender, and assumptions).²

Most contexts of life (school, the workplace, and the community) call for some levels of writing skill, and each context makes overlapping, but not identical, demands. Proficient writers can adapt their writing flexibly to the context in which it takes place. In the school setting, writing plays two distinct but complementary roles. First, it is a skill that draws on the use of strategies (such as planning, evaluating, and revising text) to accomplish a variety of goals, such as writing a report or expressing an opinion with the support of evidence. Second, writing is a means of extending and deepening students' knowledge; it acts as a tool for learning subject matter Keys.³

Because these roles are closely linked, it is recommended that language arts teachers should use content-area texts to teach reading and writing skills in which the teachers provide instruction and practice in discipline-specific reading and writing.

b. Function of Writing

There are three functions of writing skill in English teaching and learning process

- 1) The first function focuses on the products of writing by examining texts in various ways, either through their formal surface elements or their discourse structure.
- 2) The second one, loosely divided into expressivity, cognitive and situated strands, focuses on the writer and describes writing in terms of the process used to create texts.
- 3) The third emphasizes on the role that readers pay in writing, adding a social dimension to writing research by elaborating how writers engage with an audience in creating coherent texts.

People realize that writing cannot stand alone without any other supported skills, for instance, writing has relationship with reading. All researchers rely on their skills as readers, because all writers must be readers. Through reading you can

²Herrefenan et al. *Testing English as second language*. (New York: Mc. Grow Hall Book Company, 2007), p. 218

³Shanahan. *Statistic non-parametric*. (Jakarta: IKIP Yogyakarta, 2004), p. 17

understand how the language work to communicate ideas, through reading you can evaluate how vocabulary constructs together as a certain rules of grammar or how the use of spelling , grammar, punctuation, word choices, and other elements construct as a good written text. Reading helps you to be a good writer.

Writing is a psychological activity of the language user to put information in the written text. People consider that writing skill is the most difficult skill to develop. In the process of studying and acquiring new languages writing process is more complex than other skills. Writing has been a central topic in applied linguistics for many years and remains an area of lively intellectual research or debate. Many forms of enquiry have been summoned to clarify both how writing best works and how it should be best taught. Its complex structures seem constantly need adequate description and explanation.⁴

c. Types of Writing

There are five types of writing include recount text, report text, narrative text, procedure text and descriptive text.

- 1) Recount text to retell events for the purpose of informing or entertaining.
 - a) Orientation : provides the setting and introduces the participants.
 - b) Event: what happened, in what sequence.
 - c) Reorientation: optimal closure of events
- 2) Report text to describe the way things are reference to a range of natural man made and social phenomenon in our environment. The researcher will use the kind of writing based on the curriculum at the school as the place of research.
- 3) Narrative text to amuse or to entertain and to deal with actual or vicarious experience in different ways. narrative deal with problematic events which lead to a crisis or turning point of some kinds, which intend find resolution.
 - a) Orientation: sets the scene and introduces the participants.
 - b) Evaluation: a steeping back to evaluate the plight.
 - c) Complication: a crisis arises.
 - d) Resolution: the crisis is toresolved for the better or for the worse.
 - e) Reorientation: optional.

⁴*Log. Cit.* Herrefenanet al, p.215

- 4) Procedure text to describe how something is accomplished through a sequence of actions or steps.
 - a) Goal
 - b) Material
 - c) Steps (First, second, third, next, and finally)
- 5) Descriptive text to describe a particular person, place or thing.
 - a) Identification: identifies the phenomenon to be described.
 - b) Description: describes parts, qualities, characteristics.

The present researcher will be using the types of writing based on the curriculum at the school as the place of research.

d. Technique in Teaching Writing

Good writing skills are essential for effective communication. Learning to write well of course takes time and practice. There are at least five stages in constructing a good written text.⁵

1) Establishing Topics

Before writing, we should plan what we are going to write about and the purpose of the writing. After that we can start to write.

2) Organizing Ideas

Writing involves some activities before, when we write, and after writing. The activities before we write include exploring ideas which can build vocabulary, interviewing someone, discussion, etc; and organizing ideas which can order information in a paragraph, writing topic sentences, limiting information, using a time sequence, making an idea map, categorizing and making outline, summarizing ideas, writing titles, etc. For instance, someone as a speaker, before she/he transfers his/her arguments to the public she/he has to collect many opinions so the public can accept the opinion easier.

3) Revising First Draft

In revising, you can evaluate and change words you think inappropriate yet. You still have an opportunity to open your mind to get the other better ideas. Take example a teacher in teaching learning process before she/he teaches in the classroom she/he studies directly to get meaning full before she/he transfers to the

⁵Freedman, A. *English for academic purposes*. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001), p. 27-28

students.

4) Proofreading the Final Draft

After we write the first draft we sell edit and revise it. It could be the content, form, organization, cohesion and style, and grammar. In order to produce a good writing we should write more than just one draft. A good writing can be the fourth or fifth draft or even more. Like as a journalist before she/he acts her/him concepts the rules of technique so can get the good result.

e. Micro and Macro Skill of Writing

In writing, there are some aspects that have to be considered. They are the micro skills and macro skills of writing. Later they can be used in teaching writing as well as assessing writing⁶. Those skills are described as follows:

1) Micro skills

- a) Produce graphemes and orthographic patterns of English.
- b) Produce writing at an efficient rate of speed to suit the purpose.
- c) Produce an acceptable core of words and use appropriate word order patterns.
- d) Use acceptable grammatical systems (e.g., tense, agreement, and pluralization), patterns, and rules.
- e) Express a particular meaning in different grammatical forms.
- f) Use cohesive devices in written discourse.

2) Macro skills

- a) Use the rhetorical forms and conventions of written discourse.
- b) Appropriately accomplish the communicative functions of written texts according to form and purpose.
- c) Convey links and connections between events, and communicative such relations as main idea, supporting idea, new information, given information, generalization, and exemplification.
- d) Distinguish between literal and implied meanings of writing.
- e) Correctly convey culturally specific references in the context of the written text.
- f) Develop and use a battery of writing strategies, such as accurately assessing

⁶Brown, Douglas. *Language assessment principles and classroom practice*. (San Fransisco California: Longman, 2003), p. 221

audience's interpretation, using prewriting devices, writing with fluency in the first drafts, using paraphrases and synonyms, soliciting peer and instructor feedback, and using feedback for revising and editing.

In conclusion, we can say that the earlier micro skills apply more appropriately to imitative and intensive types of writing performance in which they tend to describe about the mechanical of writing and at the level of word, such as cohesive devices, past verb, and so forth. On the other hand, the macro skill covered wider areas of writing, such as the form and the communicative purpose of a written text, main idea and supporting idea, the literal and implied meaning writing, etc. thus, it is not only about a word but it is about the whole written text.

f. The Assessment of Writing Skills

In this study, the present researcher asses 5 aspects of writing skills as stated by Heaton which consists of content, organization, grammar, vocabulary, and mechanics as shown on table 1 bellow.⁷

Table 1
Writing Assessment

	1	2	3	4	5
	Very good	Good	Average	Poor	Very poor
	17-20	14-16	11-13	8-10	5-7
Content	If the central purpose, the unity, the coherence, and the continuity if the composition are all correct.	If the composition contains few errors of the central purpose, unity, coherence, and continuity.	If the composition contains some errors of the central purpose, unity, coherence, and continuity.	If the composition is dominated by errors of the central purpose, unity, coherence, and continuity.	If the central purpose, unity, coherence, and continuity are all incorrect.
Organization	If the words, sentences, and paragraphs line up easily from a clear pattern.	If the composition contains few errors of words, sentences and	If the composition contains some errors of words, sentences	If the composition is dominated by errors of the words,	If the words, sentences, and paragraphs pattern of the

⁷Heaton, J. B. *Writing English language test*, (Singapore Long - man Group Limited, 1989). P. 100

		paragraphs.	and paragraphs .	sentences and paragraphs .	composition are all incorrect.
Grammar	If the grammar of the composition is all correct.	If the composition contains occasional errors of vocabulary, but the meaning is not obscured.	If the composition contains frequent errors of vocabulary but the meaning is not obscured.	If the composition is dominated by errors of vocabulary and the meaning is confusing. Very poor.	If the vocabulary of the composition are all inappropriate.
Vocabulary	If the composition contains wide range of vocabulary and using effective words.	If the composition contains occasional errors of vocabulary but the meaning is not obscured.	If the composition contains frequent errors of vocabulary but the meaning is not obscured.	If the composition is dominated by errors of vocabulary and the meaning is confusing.	If the vocabulary of the composition are all inappropriate
Mechanics	If the punctuation, spelling, and capitalization of the composition are all correct.	If the composition contains few errors of punctuation, spelling and capitalization.	If the composition contains some errors of punctuation , spelling and capitalization.	If the composition is dominated by errors of punctuation, spelling, and capitalization.	If the punctuation, spelling, and capitalization of the composition are all incorrect.

3. Short Funtional Text

Short funtional text is a short text that has particular meaning and purpose, and can be used in our daily life. There are five types of short functional text include announcement, greeting card, invitation, notice/guidance and short message.

a. Announcement

To provide complete and clear information about certain events or occasion. Some characteristics of announcement:

1. Straightforward and ease the readers to get information quickly
2. Keep it short, inviting, and to the point.
3. Clear and complete
4. For a bad news, make a direct and no-nonsense statement.

b. Greeting Card

Greeting Cards functions as an expression of sympathy and care to others.

The purpose is to congratulate someone' achievement, express sympathy on someone's, and motivate someone on gaining achievement. Some characteristics of greeting card:

1. Clarify a clear purpose
2. Use an appraisal diction
3. Accurate address

c. Invitation

Function/Purpose is to o invite someone to attend an occasion. The Structure/Parts: The addressee (the person invited), salutation, the message (the content of the message), and the Sender. Some characteristics of invitation:

1. Having an accurate address
2. Giving clear time, place, and activity
3. Providing sufficient information about the inviter
4. Expressing that the writer is looking forward to seeing person
5. If there is a dress code, state it in the lower left-hand corner

d. Notice/Guidance

The Functions of notice/guidance:

1. Prohibition notifies people not to do something. People may find this kind of notice in a public places.
2. Caution or warning warns people to be careful in handling something. Ignoring the notice may cause injury or breaking the facilities.
3. Guidance gives information to people to do something appropriately.

4. The informational notice provides information that could be useful for people.

e. Short Message

Its function is to send an important message to other people. Some characteristics of a short message :

1. Clear addressee (someone who receives the message)
2. Straight forward
3. If it is an instruction state it clearly.

(<http://shortfunctionaltext.blogspot.com/>)

4. General Concept of Email

Email is a computer based method of sending messages from one computer user to another.⁸These messages usually consist of individual pieces of text which you can send to another computer user even if the other user is not logged in (i.e. using the computer) at the time you send your message. The message can then be read at a later time. This procedure is analogous to sending and receiving a letter. Originally, email messages were restricted to simple text, but now many systems can handle more complicated formats, such as graphics and word processed documents.

When mail is received on a computer system, it is usually stored in an electronic mailbox for the recipient to read later. Electronic mailboxes are usually special files on a computer which can be accessed using various commands. Each user normally has their individual mailbox. It is straightforward to send electronic mail between users of different computer systems which are connected to major networks. Most major academic and research institutions and companies throughout the world can now be reached by electronic mail. In addition, a growing number of individuals can be contacted in this way. In the UK, most academic and research institutions are linked by a network called JANET (or Super JANET). This is effectively part of the Internet, so email can be exchanged with most national and international networks.

⁸Andini, Zeva. *Teaching narrative paragraph for second grade of senior high school through email*. (Faculty Teacher Training and Education English of University of Ibn Khaldun Bogor. Unpublished. S-1 thesis. 2010), p. 8

a. Basic Email Skill in Teaching Writing Skills

Before starting to use email with learners, you will need to check that your learners have certain basic skills in place. Learners need to be familiar not only with the mechanics of sending and receiving email in teaching writing skills and also attachment, but also with the kind of language used in email, as well as the rules of engagement or netiquette, required in email use. Basic skills may be considered in two groups: communication skills and technical; skills.⁹

a. Communication skills

It is a good idea to remind learners that, as in traditional letter writing, there are levels of formality in email writing. An email written to enquire about a job vacancy will have a different level of formality to an email sent to a close friend. While the email to a friend may include abbreviations, emoticons, misspellings or lower-case characters, such as these are entirely inappropriate for a more formal email.

Composing an email has the added advantage for learners of allowing them to draft and edit before sending that the text of narrative paragraph. Research shows that this part of the writing process, so much easier than with pen and paper, is something that learners appreciate. But communication by email is of course still very fast. And make the simple ways of writing English skill in narrative paragraph.

b. Technical skills

Apart from basic word processing and typing skills, learners will need to have an email account. Many learners will already have a personal or work email account that they will be willing to use for their language class work, but others may need help with setting up a new email account.

There are several free, web-based email services, through which it is easy to set up and use an email account. The best known are Yahoo, Hotmail, or Google Mail, although Google Mail currently requires you to receive an invitation from an already registered Google Mail user for you to be able to open an account.

⁹Atmiyanti, Nyai Dahlia. *Teaching writing recount text through email*. Faculty Teacher Training and Education English of University of Ibn Khaldun Bogor. Unpublished.S-1 thesis, 2010), p. 13

b. Advantages and Disadvantages of Using Email for Teaching

Related to Jack Pillemer's experience in tutoring with email, the following are the advantages and disadvantages of using email as teaching tool:

1) Advantages of using email

- a) E-mail correspondence increases motivation to write.
- b) The EFL student tends to feel responsible for what s\he has written since it is personal (meaningful). S/he is reflected through the words and ideas and someone will actually read what has been written and respond to it. The response will be completely different from a teacher's response.
- c) E-mail definitely excites, motivates and encourages writing.
- d) The student's written expressions improve during the process.
- e) Computer will help the students with punctuation, spelling and appropriate words in the sentences they made.
- f) Email is information technology that very easy to acquire and can force the students to write voluntarily,¹⁰
- g) The steps of using email in teaching learning process was given in computer based assistant, data on students' progress are available continually and can be used formatively
- h) Linguistic, cultural and educational diversity in the writing classroom are easily addressed in assessment because email can be individualized.

2) Disadvantages of using email

- a) Not all of the students wrote their letters and certainly not all at the same time. The partner school sometime didn't reply immediately.
- b) Some of the students wrote very short letters because still confuse how and what they will write about.
- c) The technical organization should not fall on the teacher's shoulders alone. We need more people to help with the technical appliances.
- d) We need more time to prepare the class.
- e) Having the same program between two school/class which got involves in our email program sometimes very difficult to arrange.

¹⁰Dudenev, Gavin & Nicky Hockly. *How to teach English with technology*. (Edinburgh Gate: Pearson Education Limited, 2007), p. 64

- f) Teacher who want to use email as his/her teaching tool must be aware that the school must have more than 10 computer set and internet link.
- g) This element is perhaps the most important of all. A well-structured, well-planned environment must exist. The teacher must know who has sent letters and who hasn't. A solution to the technical problems of each student must be found. Organized work groups around students with e-mail access are a good idea. The teacher should know who is in each group and be aware of problems.
- h) Regular lessons should be scheduled to deal with the project. During these lesson students share information, prepare for the next letter, discuss interesting facts that they have learned, still need much time.

A mutual obligation to make the project succeed must be established with the foreign teacher, which means the teacher should do extra preparation to start the email writing class.

D. The Use of Email in Teaching Writing Skills

Email is one of the most spectacular inventions in the world around 19 century. It's become the most used and useful information and communication technology (ICT) tools around today. Email helps us communicate with a lot of people around the world in easy, simple and cheap ways. Email allows us to keep in touch with other teacher around the world and also with some professionals via mailing list or discussion groups. The students can exchange their experience in teaching and learning process. And email helps the teacher to communicate with their students outside the classroom, for example setting, receiving, marking and returning homework and other written assignment. Email can helps students to improve their self by exchange experience and knowledge with other students from different school or country. In the key pal project, email projects set up between learners in different classes or countries.

Reading and writing emails gives the students motivation to write and more eager to know the target language because they want to communicate easily with their friends from the country of the target language. One of the biggest advantages of using email with learners from the teacher's point of view is that the technology is relatively simple to use, and most of our learners will already be familiar with it. If

our learners are not familiar with email, it is not difficult to teach them to use it, and the technology is both easy and free.¹¹

Composing an email has the added advantage for learners because it's allowing them to draft and edit before sending. It is shows that this part of the writing process so much easier than with the pen and paper is something those learners appreciates. And communication by email is of course still very fast.

Before we start to use email in our teaching learning process, we need to teach the students the rules of netiquette. These are 'rules' of effective online communication. Well-known netiquette rules include:

1. Not using only capital letters, which is perceived as 'shouting' online.
2. Being sure to respect others' opinions.
3. Avoiding 'flaming'- ongoing arguments which become increasingly personalized and possibly public.
4. Making sure that files sent as email attachments are not too large, as the person receiving the email may not be able to download them.
5. Point out that culture differences are important, and that allowances must be made when writing to people abroad. Cross culture understanding is needed in this case.

Most teachers and students being familiar with email these days, this is an ideal medium for getting your classes interacting with other students around the world. One of the best ways of doing this is by organizing an email keypal exchange with other students in another country. This is immensely motivating for students, as the combination of technology, speed of communication and writing for a 'real' audience combine to provide the sort of experience which is difficult to create in the classroom alone.

E. Research Methodology

1. Research Design

This study was categorized as pre-experimental research design. One group pre-test and post-test design (pre-experimental) usually involves three steps: (1) administering a pre-test which measuring the dependent variable; (2) applying the

¹¹*Ibid.* Dudeney, Gavin & Nicky Hockly. p. 62

experimental treatment to the subjects; and (3) administering a post-test, again measuring the dependent variable. Differences attributed in application of the experimental treatment are evaluated by comparing the pre-test and post-test scores.¹²

In this research design there is no control group. The present researcher gave pre-test to the student, then, present researcher gave them treatment, after treatment has done, present researcher gave the student post-test.

Table 2
One Group Pre-test and Post-test Design

Pre-test	Independent	Post-test
Y_1	X	Y_2

Notes:

- Y_1 : Pre-test
- X : Treatment independent variable;
- Y_2 : Post-test

2. Setting of the Study

The setting of study refers to where and when the research is going to be conducted. In this case, the present researcher undertook the research at the eighth graders of *MTs. Mu'allimat NW Kelayu* while the time in conducting this research started on March until May 2018.

3. Population and Sample of the Study

The whole of the research subject is called population research. It is in line with the Encyclopedia of Educational Evaluation. She also states that a population is a set (or collection) of all elements possessing one or more attributes of interest.¹³

The population of this research the eighth grader of *MTs. Mu'allimat NW Kelayu* in the school year 2017-2018. The population consisted of two classes which were 39 students.

¹²Ary et al. *Introduction to research in education (8th ed)*. (Wodsworth. Cengage Learning, 2010),

¹³Arikunto. *Prosedur penelitian suatu pendekatan praktiki disirevisi*: (Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta, 2010), p. 173

4. Data Collection.

1. Identification of variables

Based on the title of this study, there were two variables in this study as follows:

- a. Email is independent variable.
- b. Writing skills is dependent variable.

2. Definition of Variables

- a. Email is a computer based method of sending messages from one computer user to another. Media through email is one of the most important things for teachers to teaching writing effectively.
- b. Writing Skills is a psychological activity of the language user to put information in the written text.

3. Instrument of the Study

In scientific research, instrument is very important to use by the researcher in order to measure the students' achievement as the sample of the research. Research instrument is a device used by the research while collecting the data to make work become easier and to get better result, complete and systematic in order to make the data easy to be processed.¹⁴

a. Test

Instrument is a tool which is used to collect the data. A test as a set of questions or exercises or other tests which is used to measure skill, knowledge, intelligence, achievement, and attitude of someone or a group of people.

In this research, the present researcher used the test namely is written test, which was taken from the eighth graders of junior high school book. The test was given to sample and the result was gathered as the data of this research. In this case, the test was in form of written which had instruction on it. The instruction was asking the student to write a letter.

Test is an exercise in measuring skill, knowledge, intelligent, and attitude of someone or a group of people. The test that is used in research depends on the type and objective of the research itself. In this test of writing a letter, there were some

¹⁴*Ibid.* Arikunto, 2010).p. 192

elements that evaluate, such as : Content, Organization, Vocabular, Grammar dan Mechanics.

b. Validity of Instrument

The validity of a test is the extent to which is measured what it is supposed to measure.¹⁵ The aim of it will measure the skill, knowledge, ability, etc. The series of pictures use to stimulate the subject to build their opinion. The test used must be appropriate in term of our subject, the dependable in the evidence provides, and applicable to our particular situation. The researcher will ask the students to make a short functional text in the form of memo using their email which will be prepared by the researcher in 90 minutes. Furthermore, the students' writing will be scored based on the contents, grammar, vocabulary, mechanics, and organization aspects.¹⁶

To measure the students' ability in writing skill using email, the present researcher was the criteria which are quoted from Heaton.¹⁷ Those are:

Table 3
The table of criteria is as follows:

No	Evaluated aspects	Score criteria	Result
1	<i>Content</i>	15-20	Excellent to very good
		10-15	Good to average
		5-10	Fair to poor
		0-5	Very poor
2	<i>Organization</i>	15-20	Excellent to very good
		10-15	Good to average
		5-10	Fair to poor
		0-5	Very poor
3	<i>Vocabulary</i>	15-20	Excellent to very good
		10-15	Good to average
		5-10	Fair to poor
		0-5	Very poor
4	<i>Grammar</i>	15-20	Excellent to very good
		10-15	Good to average
		5-10	Fair to poor
		0-5	Very poor
5	<i>Mechanics</i>	15-20	Excellent to very good
		10-15	Good to average
		5-10	Fair to poor
		0-5	Very poor

¹⁵*Op. Cit.* Heaton, J. B., p. 159

¹⁶*Ibid.* Heaton, J. B. p. 89

¹⁷*Ibid.* Heaton, J. B. p. 146

Total score	100-10
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c. Readability instrument

The readability as the sum total (including the interactions) of all those elements within a given piece of printed material that affects the success a group of readers have with it. The test can be said that it is successful if the students can understand it, read it at an optimum speed, and find it interesting.

It means that if the instrument is tested to some students out of the sample group, they understand the instructions of the test and do as what has been instructed. In other word, the instruction of the writing test should be clear and easy to understand. It is essential that the researcher obtains feedback to check that the instrument instructions have been understood before the instrument is used in this research.

4. Technique of Data Collection

In collecting data the present researcher lists some steps as follows:

5. Pre-test

The pre-test applied before teaching the students by using email.

6. Treatment

After giving the pre-test, the students treated by using email. The treatments was place within 4 meeting and took 90 minutes for each meeting.

7. Post-test

The present researcher gave the post-test to the students. However, the post-test was used after the present researcher implemented the treatment to the experimental group by using email.

E. Data Analysis

1. Descriptive Statistic

In this research, the data was analyzed by using descriptive statistic. It is to know the mean score and standars deviation. Mean score was analyzed by using the following formula :

$$M = \frac{\sum X}{N}$$

Where :

- M = Mean Score
- $\sum x$ = The total of students score
- N = The number of students

Where the Standar Deviation was analyzed by using the following formula:

$$Sd = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2}{N}}$$

Where :

- SD = Standar Deviation
- $\sum x$ = The total of students score
- N = The number of students

2. Statistics Required for Testing Hypothesis

The requirements in formulating hypothesis such as :¹⁸

- a. Hypothesis must be formulated clearly and briefly.
- b. Hypothesis must be obviously indicate the relation between two or more variables, and
- c. Hypothesis must be supported by theories which are proposed by the expert or based on relevant investigation.

3. Testinghypothesis

Even though not all of the investigation require hypothesis, but at least the hypothesis is needed in the investigation. Therefore, hypothesis should be formulated before starting investigation. Some requirements in formulating hypothesis, such as: (1) hypothesis must be formulated clearly and briefly, (2) hypothesis must indicate obviously about the relationship between two or more variables, and (2) hypothesis must be supported by the theories which are proposed by the experts or based on the relevant investigation.

Hypothesis constitutes a temporal answer or a weak answer where the truth remains to be proved, therefore, the hypothesis proposed in this research remains to

¹⁸*Op. Cit.* Ary et al, 2010

be proved. However, the alternative hypothesis (H_a) should be changed into null hypothesis first. In testing hypothesis H_a must be changed into H_o .

To test the hypothesis, the present researcher used r_{test} . The formula used:

$$r_{test} = \frac{n \sum y_1 y_2 - (\sum y_1)(\sum y_2)}{\sqrt{(n \sum y_1^2 - (\sum y_1)^2)(n \sum y_2^2 - (\sum y_2)^2)}}$$

Notes:

$$r_{test} = r_{test}$$

n = total of sample

y_1 = pre test

y_2 = post test.

And then, the criteria will be used as follows:

- If the value of r_{test} is high than r_{table} ($r_{test} > r_{table}$), H_a (Alternative Hypothesis) was accepted. It means that there is significant effect of email on student writing skill.
- If the value of r_{test} is lower than r_{table} ($r_{test} < r_{table}$), H_o (Alternative Hypothesis) was rejected. It means that there is no effect of email on student writing skill.

F. Results And Discussion

1. Descriptive Statistics

The present researcher described the result of the study that has been conducted before. The objective of this study found out the effect of email on students' writing skill at the eight graders of *MTs. Mu'allimat NW Kelayu*. To obtain the data, the present researcher used writing test as the instruments of the study.

The result of data analysis showed that the mean and standard deviation, the higher score on pre test was 26 and the lower score was 16 with the total mean 20.4 and standard deviation 20.6 while on post test the higher score was 29 and the lower score was 23 with the total mean 27.0 and standard deviation 27.1

1. Testing Hypothesis

The objective of this study found out the effect of email on students' writing skill at the eight graders of *MTs. Mu'allimat NW Kelayu*. Based on the result of

calculation, found that r_{test} was 0.52. Then, after consulting it to r_{table} with $df = 5\%$ was 0.38. So, r_{test} was higher than r_{table} ($0.52 > 0.38$). Thus, it can be concluded that there was the effect of email on students' writing skill.

2. Discussion

After obtaining and calculating the data, the present researcher discusses the result of this study. The result of the study answered the statement of the problems.

1. Based on the result of hypothesis testing, the present researcher found that there was effect of email on students' writing skill. It can be seen on the result of r_{test} was higher than r_{table} ($0.52 > 0.38$). So, the hypothesis alternative was accepted and null hypothesis was rejected.
2. The extents of the effect of email on students' writing skill after finding out the result of this research the present researcher found the extents of the effect of email on students' writing skill. Based on the result hypothesis testing the present researcher found that 0.52 was categorized into sufficient because in the table interval indicated that the score between 0.40– 0.59 was categorized into sufficient.

G. Conclusion And Suggestions

1. Conclusion

Referring the result and discussion of the study, the present researcher concludes as follows:

- a. Based on the result of hypothesis testing, the present researcher found that r_{test} was higher than r_{table} ($0.52 > 0.38$). So, it could be concluded that there was the effect of email on students' writing skill.
- b. The extents of the effect of email on students' writing skill was categorized into insufficient that the score between 0.40 – 0.59.

2. Suggestion

- a. Teachers have to be selective in choosing a suitable method in teaching and learning process. Teachers have to know what students need in teaching and learning process, so that it makes students feel comfort during teaching and learning process.
- b. The use of media cannot be separated from teaching and learning

- process. The use of email is very helpful for teachers during teaching and learning process.
- c. The present researcher hopes that teachers may create an interactive teaching and learning process in order to make students more active in giving responses to the material.
 - d. The present researcher hopes that students are more interested in English lessons.

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